

Genistein as a neuroprotective agent: a comprehensive review of its potential in neurodegenerative diseases

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Abstract: Neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) are generally identified by the sudden decrease in neuronal disruption in normal and subsequent cell death in the brain or peripheral nervous system underlying conditions, such as Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, Huntington's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, lack of effective treatments shown to slow down their progression. Natural compounds derived from plants have demonstrated potential efficacy in combating various diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders. This review article evaluates the molecular targets and therapeutic potential of isoflavones, with a particular focus on genistein, in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. Both *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies have indicated the neuroprotective effects against NDDs. We aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the role played by genistein in delaying the development, mechanisms of action and progression of neurodegenerative diseases. Additionally, we examine the current evidence supporting the use of genistein in preclinical and clinical studies, highlighting its potential therapeutic benefits in neurodegenerative disorders. However, further research is needed to elucidate optimal dosage, bioavailability, and long-term safety profiles, also to investigate potential synergistic effects with existing therapies. The insights provided in this review may contribute to the development of novel therapeutic strategies for the management of these devastating disorders.

Keywords: Neurodegenerative diseases; Genistein; Neuropharmacological properties; Ischemia stroke

1. Introduction

Genistein (GEN) is a naturally occurring isoflavone found primarily in species of the legume family [1], including Glycine max (soybean), Lupine (*Lupinus albus* L.), Psoralea (*Psoralea corylifolia* L.), and broad bean (*Vicia faba* L.) [2]. GEN exhibits numerous beneficial properties for human health such as alleviation of osteoporosis, cardiovascular diseases, menopausal symptoms, cytotoxic abilities as well as neuroprotection [3]. The dietary intake of GEN is relatively higher (2530 mg/day) in the Asian population because their diet consists of foods made from soybeans, e.g., B. Natto, tofu and sufu (which are rich in GEN). GEN, like other polyphenols, has an oral bioavailability of approximately 10% [4]. Due to its low absorption potential, lipophilic nature and low molecular weight [5], GEN is passively transported to the intestinal cells [6].

In most industrialized countries, neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) such as Parkinson's disease (PD) [11], Huntington's disease (HD) [10], and Alzheimer's disease (AD) [9] are the main problem and economic pressure on the healthcare system [8]. An estimated prevalence has indicated that worldwide, both the number and the proportion of age-related NDDs will increase over the next few years [7]. The number of Americans ages 65 and older affected by Alzheimer's disease is expected to increase from 56 million in 2020 to 88 million in 2050 [13]. PD incidence rates are projected to vary between 8 and 18 per 100,000 person-years in the general population, equivalent to 1.0% in those over 60 and 3.0% in those over 80 [12]. In Europe, estimated prevalence rates of Parkinson's disease range from 65 to 12,500 per 100,000 or 5 to 346 per 100,000 person-years [14]. Genetic, biochemical, and molecular pathogens often contribute to the clinical presentation of NDDs, which are typically associated with marked neuronal loss and impairment of multiple functional systems [15]. Various studies support the involvement of oxidative stress, autophagy, mitochondrial dysfunction, inflammatory events, and neurotransmitter modulation in the development of NDDs [16]. Oxidative stress promotes neuronal cell death caused by the degeneration of neurons and alters intracellular signalling pathways [17]. Oxidative Stress (OS) leads to excessive Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) production that damages cells [18]. It is a situation in which the balance between the formation of ROS and the level of antioxidants is seriously disturbed [19]. ROS contribute to the development of neurodegeneration by reducing the function of biomolecules [20]. GEN may potentially reduce the process of neurodegeneration, specifically by inhibiting the inflammatory responses of microglia and protecting brain neurons from free radical damage [21]. The

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purpose of this review is to examine the physical, chemical, and neuroprotective properties of GEN in order to understand its associated mechanism of action [22, 23]. Additionally, various studies investigating the downstream signaling pathways involved in possible neuroprotective mechanisms of GEN were evaluated in this review to further future research to develop GEN as a potential neuroprotective drug [24, 25].

2. Genistein

GEN was discovered in 1899 in the Dyer's broom *Genista tinctoria*. In 1926, the core of GEN was developed after its laboratory synthesis in 1928 [25]. The deoxybenzoin (2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone) and the chalcone routes are the two conventional methods for the synthesis of GEN [26]. Other processes include flavanone rearrangement, chalcone epoxide rearrangement and cyclization [27], palladium-catalyzed cross-coupling of 3-halochromones with arylboronic acids [28], and organ lead-mediated arylation of chroman-4-ones, etc [29]. 5,7-Dihydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-chromen-4-one is the chemical name of GEN [30]. It is an organic substance that is chemically like mammalian oestrogens. Although GEN is found in different plant species, it has been extracted from fermentation broths of several microorganisms (*Streptomyces* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp.) [31]. It has since been found to occur as a major secondary metabolite in *Trifolium* species and in *Glycine max* L. (synonym *Soya hispida*) [32]. The biologically active glucoside genistein is the main dietary source of genistein [33]. The sugar molecule of isoflavone glycoside, is released during fermentation or digestion of soybeans or soy products, leaving behind the isoflavone aglycone. Isoflavones are the main phenolic compounds found in soybeans [34]. The chemical structure of Genistein is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Chemical Structure of Genistein (GEN)

3. Chemical Properties

The molecular structure of GEN is related to that of 17-estradiol (E2), an endogenous oestrogen that acts predominantly through the ERs in humans. GEN consists of two aromatic rings (A and B) linked by a heterocyclic pyran ring (C) as shown in Figure 1 and the different biosynthesis pathways are shown in Figure 2 [35]. ER ligands typically consist of two hydroxyl groups separated by a rigid hydrophobic linker region [36]. In addition, an effective ligand possesses a phenolic hydroxyl group, since ligand recognition is achieved through a mixture of specific hydrogen bonds between the ligand and the ER. Both GEN and 17-beta-estradiol share structural features of the phenol ring and the gap between its 4- and 7-group -OH moieties is 11.5 [37]. These properties allow it to bind to oestrogen or testosterone receptor proteins [38]. GEN possesses both anti-androgenic and anti-estrogenic properties by interacting with estradiol or testosterone for their respective proteins, some of the therapeutic effect of GEN in different *in-vivo* models are given in Table 1 [39].

Figure 2 Biosynthesis of GEN: (A) Synthesis through Deoxybenzoin route. (B) Synthesis through Chalcone route

Table 1 Therapeutic effect of GEN in different in-vivo models.

SN	Dose and Route	Animal/Cell Lines	Experimental Model	Outcome
1.	30 μ M	HEK293-T cells.	CIP2A induced APP/tau Phosphorylation and A β production.	Reduced APP/tau hyperphosphorylation and A β production.
2.	1.0 μ M	SH-SY5Y Cell Line.	β -Amyloid Peptide (1–42)–induced genotoxicity and cell death.	Decreased genotoxicity and death cell induced by A β (1–42).
3.	125 μ M	SH-SY5Y and RIN-m5F.	A β - or hIAPP (human islet amylin peptides)-induced toxicity.	GEN exhibited dual inhibition activity against both A β and hIAPP aggregation and toxicity.
4.	Genistein orally given (10, 50, or 100 mg/kg)	Male albino Wistar rats 190–230 g.	LPS-induced cognitive dysfunctions and neural inflammation.	Improved cognitive functions by reducing neuroinflammation through attenuation of oxidative stress and AChE and appropriate modulation of Nrf2/NF- κ B/IL-6/TNF α /COX2/iNOS/TLR4/GFAP.
5.	Genistein orally given (10mg/kg)	Adult male Wistar rats 250–300 g.	A β -induced impairment of short-term spatial memory.	GEN pre-treatment ameliorates Ab-induced impairment of short-term spatial memory in rats through an estrogenic pathway and by inducing attenuation of oxidative stress.
6.	Genistein dose (150 mg/kg/day)	Male Wistar rats 350g.	Streptozotocin-induced rat model of the sporadic form of AD.	High dose of GEN can activate the autophagy mediated correction of AD.
7.	Genistein (10, 20, and 40 mg/kg)	Mice (20–22 g).	Scopolamine (Scop)-induced amnesia.	GEN could alleviate Scop-induced amnesia in mice through promoting the cholinergic neurotransmission, enhancing antioxidant system, and activating the ERK/CREB/BDNF signalling.

4. Neuropharmacological properties of GEN

4.1. Role of GEN in Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive irreversible brain disease characterized by abnormal protein aggregation such as amyloid peptide (A) and tau proteins. Aggregation of A increases reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation in the brain, leading to oxidative stress that induces neuronal apoptosis. In turn, ROS increases A production by decreasing alpha-secretase activity, promotes expression and activation of beta- and gamma-secretase, and upregulation of PS1 and BACE1 expression mediated via c-Jun N-terminal activation Kinase (JNK) signalling pathway in various brain regions, particularly in the hippocampus and in neocortical areas (major brain regions involved in memory) [36]. The abnormal protein aggregation triggers intracellular apoptotic (Bcl2, Bax, caspases) and inflammatory (tumor necrosis factor) signalling pathways leading to the degeneration of neurons involved in memory functions [37].

In the search for new drugs to treat and treat AD, flavonoids are at the forefront. GEN, an isoflavonoid, is being actively studied for its potential anti-AD benefits. Various studies (*in vitro* and *in vivo*) have shown that GEN is able to prevent neurological diseases by employing proteins that promote survival at apoptosis, increase antioxidant gene expression and minimize amyloid-beta production. Wang and colleagues showed that GEN administration reduced neuronal loss in the hippocampus by inhibiting mitochondrial apoptotic proteins (caspase-3, Bax and cytochrome c), thereby improving learning and memory in rats [38]. Furthermore, GEN alleviated lipopolysaccharide-induced cognitive dysfunction by attenuating neuronal inflammation, oxidative stress, and cholinergic dysfunction. In pheochromocytoma cells (PC12), GEN blocked caspase-3 activity along with JNK activation, followed by repression of JNK-dependent ones the Fas/FasL pathway in A(25-35) induced synaptic dysfunction and decreased intracellular calcium levels. Due to the ability of GEN to decrease intracellular calcium levels, the presynaptic marker of SYN and the postsynaptic marker of PSD-95 induced by A(25-35) became associated with the expression of CaM/CaMKII/CREB signalling pathway upregulated. A different research investigation discovered that GEN demonstrated the capacity to enhance cognitive functions, reduce hippocampal neuron degeneration, and elevate the levels of specific proteins or mRNA expression, including GRP78, CHOP, Caspase-12, Cle-Caspase-9, Cle-Caspase-3, PERK, and a decrease in p-PERK [39].

4.2. Role of GEN in Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a diverse neurological disorder characterized by a significant and gradual drop in dopamine levels in the substantia nigra pars compacta, striatum, and motor deficits such as slowness of movement, stiffness, and rigidity [40]. Lewy bodies, intracellular inclusions of aggregated α -Synuclein is one of the pathological signs of Parkinson's disease and occurs in the dorsal motor nucleus, olfactory bulb and nucleus (SNc) [41]. Neuronal demise in Parkinson's disease is believed to be driven by apoptosis, extensive oxidative stress, and persistent inflammation. Apoptosis involves various initiator caspases (such as Casp-8 and Casp-9) and executor caspases (including Casp-3, -6, and -7) and can occur through intrinsic or extrinsic pathways. The intrinsic pathway, often referred to as the mitochondrial-mediated pathway, is activated by initiator caspase-9. Recent studies suggest that estrogen and estrogen-like compounds could be potential treatments for neurodegenerative diseases, including Parkinson's disease. Genistein, a naturally occurring isoflavone present in soy products, possesses estrogenic properties. Liu and colleagues have demonstrated that the phytoestrogen GEN, akin to estrogen, exhibits neuroprotective effects against MPTP-induced neuronal damage in the nigrostriatal system [42]. In another *in vitro* study, human SH-SY5Y cells overexpressing the A53T variant alpha-synuclein were used as a model for Parkinson's disease. Genistein has been shown to inhibit oxidative stress damage and cell death in these cells by activating oestrogen receptors and NFE2L2 channels [43]. Furthermore, it was discovered that genistein possesses protective properties by reducing 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA)-induced apoptotic cell death in nerve growth factor (NGF)-differentiated PC12 cells. Du and co-workers found that GENs that reduce LPS-induced nigro-striatal damage in an ovariectomized rat model of Parkinson's disease can also prevent microglia overactivation and protect dopaminergic neurons via GPER and IGF-1R signalling pathways [44]. Furthermore, another *in vitro* study revealed that GEN elicits anti-inflammatory activity against LPS-induced microglial activation by inhibiting iNOS expression by transcription factors (IRF-1 and pSTAT1) [45] and expression of IL-6 and MCP-1 inhibits, indicating neuroprotection against Parkinson's disease [46].

4.3. Role of GEN in Huntington's disease

Huntington's disease (HD) is a neurological disorder characterized by the loss of striatal neurons in the brain and mutations in the huntingtin (HTT) gene, which in turn lead to an increase in CAG repeats [47]. Henceforth, a long tract with glutamine residues develops (the PolyQ tract, (mutated HTT), which causes neuronal dysfunction and eventually neurodegeneration [48]. The most typical signs and symptoms include motor, cognitive and mental impairments as well as weight loss, sleep problems and dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system [49]. GEN is being studied for its potential use in treating Huntington's disease. Pierzynowska and colleagues examined an *in vitro* study on pooled fibroblast cell lines from 4 HD patients, where genistein (30, 60 and 100 M) showed a beneficial effect on HD fibroblasts and normalization of HTT levels in HD fibroblasts [50]. Another study found that in HEK-293 the mutant cell gene 150 mg/kg/day exerts a protective effect by triggering autophagy, which consequently repaired the mutant phenotype. Activation of autophagy corrected the HD phenotype and some of the drugs when given in combination to GEN show different effects as given in Table 2 [51].

Table 1 Various class of drug which are used for treatment of NDDs along with GEN

Pathology	Act as	Effective	Drug(s)+GEN	Drug kinetics effect
Parkinson's disease (PD)	Dopamine supplement. 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) decarboxylase inhibitor. Catechol-o-methyltransferase (COMT) Inhibitor. Monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitor. Dopamine agonist. Antagonist of NMDA receptor. Anticholinergics drug.	Most potent in the case of bradykinesia. Improves therapeutic benefits of levodopa. Improves therapeutic benefits of levodopa. Improves therapeutic benefits of levodopa. Delayed onset of dyskinesia. Antidyskinetic drug. Young patients dominated by tremor.	Levodopa Carbidopa Tolcapone Selegiline Apomorphine Amantadine Trihexyphenidyl and benztropine.	Decreases metabolism with Genestin.
Alzheimer's disease (AD)	Acetyl cholinesterase inhibitor Antagonist of NMDA receptor	Dementia	Donepezil, Rivastigmine, Galantamine, Memantine	Decreases metabolism with Genestin leading increase in serum levels.
Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS)	Antagonist of NMDA receptor Antioxidant	Slow down disease progression	Riluzole Edaravone	Decreases metabolism and excretion with Genestin leading increase in serum levels.
Huntington's disease (HD)	Antichorea drug	Chorea	Tetrabenazine, Reserpine, and Deutetrabenazine.	Decreases metabolism with Genestin.

4.4. Role of GEN in Ischemic Stroke

A stroke is a serious brain disorder caused by blockage of blood vessels due to a disruption in blood flow to the brain and a lack of oxygen in the affected area. The pathogenesis of ischemic stroke includes inflammation of neurons, cellular excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, and cell death pathways [52]. The PI3K/Akt pathway is involved in glutamate excitotoxicity, calcium control and apoptosis [53]. OS is caused by a pro-oxidant/antioxidant imbalance that leads to an excess of reactive oxygen species. In addition, there is an upregulation of Notch-1 and other signalling pathways (caspases, bcl-2/Bax), including inflammatory mediator (NF-B), p53 leads to apoptosis [54]. Inflammation is triggered by decreased blood flow, activation of intravascular leukocytes, and release of pro-inflammatory mediators such as interleukin-1 (IL-1) [55]. Tumor necrosis factor (TNF) can cause further tissue damage. A wealth of studies indicates that soy-based genistein, one of the most widely used isoflavone chemicals, can potentially prevent stroke symptoms [56]. The potential pharmacological function of GEN is linked to its capacity to inhibit the nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and Akt signaling pathway, its direct antioxidant effects, and its ability to target estrogen and androgen-related molecular pathways. These actions collectively contribute to reducing the impact of strokes, extending cell survival, and offering therapeutic benefits [57]. Xie and his research team illustrated that treatment with GSS (Genistein-3'-sodium sulfonate) enhances neurological performance, reduces the size of cerebral infarction, diminishes the levels of proinflammatory cytokines, and deactivates the phosphorylation of JAK2 and STAT3 in rats with I/RI [58]. GSS also heightened the expression of 7nAChR [59, 60]. Other findings revealed the Genistein treatment reduced neuronal apoptosis caused by I/R damage in ovariectomized rats via activating the PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathway [59]. Moreover, GSS shields cortical neurons in rats from damage resulting from localized cerebral ischemia in both laboratory-based and live models. It achieves this by elevating the Bcl-2/Bax expression ratio and reducing the activity of Caspase 3. [61].

4.5. Role of GEN in Epilepsy

Epilepsy is a long-term NDD characterized by repetitive convulsions followed by abrupt stereotyped episodes with concomitant alterations in motor activity, sensation, and behavioural change [62]. It occurs due to a relative imbalance of glutamate and GABA, which leads to a change in the expression of proteins, which in turn leads to the potential development of neuronal inflammation, epilepsy in oxidative and nitrostatic stress [63]. During the prolonged state of epileptogenesis, OS continues to increase the level of biomarkers such as the cystine/glutamate transporter, iNOS, the transcription factor Nrf2, and the ratio of reduced and oxidized glutathione (GSSG/GSH) that regulate the cascades of neuroinflammation such as NF- κ B, RIPK, MAPK, ERK, JNK, and JAK-STAT signaling pathways that produce mitochondrial dysfunction and promote hyperexcitability in the forebrain of immature and adult human animal models [64]. In addition, hyperexcitability causes a progressive alteration in intracellular Ca²⁺ homeostasis that alters neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission [67], making neurons more sensitive to increased stress and leading to energy failure and neuronal death [65]. Hu and colleagues found that genistein can induce the antioxidant stress Keap1/Nrf2 signaling pathway while suppressing microglia and astrocyte activation [68]. GEN also suppresses the JAK2-STAT3 inflammatory pathway and apoptotic protein production while increasing the number of surviving neurons, providing protection against epilepsy induced brain damage [66].

4.6. Role of GEN in Depression

Depression is characterized by aversion to actions, bad mood, effects on behaviour, emotions and feelings, and perceptions of well-being. Major depressive illness is not only one of the most common and devastating mental disorders worldwide, but also a major societal and economic problem [70]. In addition, older women, especially those going through menopause, are more likely to develop this disease than younger women [69]. One reason postmenopausal women are more likely to suffer from depression than men and younger women is that in addition to everyday physiological and psychological stress, endogenous oestrogen levels also decrease. As previously demonstrated, the monoamine hypothesis, which points to a deficit or abnormalities in monoamine neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine as a cause of sadness, has been the dominant theme of depression research for about 50 years [71]. In recent years, depression and suicidal behaviour have been associated with disorders of structural and synaptic plasticity. One of the most important neurotrophic factors, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is essential for the maintenance and survival of neurons as well as synaptic plasticity. Several pieces of evidence suggest that BDNF with BDNF expression plays a role in depression. Because miRNAs are lower in depressed people, they have also been described as non-invasive potential biomarkers for identifying individuals at high risk of developing depression [72]. Indeed, microRNAs (miRNAs) hold a significant regulatory function across all stress-triggered biological signaling pathways. They represent one of the swiftest and most dynamic response mechanisms with the ability to control both gene transcription and protein translation in reaction to stress [73]. Several studies have shown that genistein is a phytoestrogen with selective oestrogen receptor modulatory effects in depression [74]. Kageyama and colleagues found that administration of 10 mg/kg to ovariectomized rats of GEN, which modulates monoamine metabolism, specifically serotonergic activity [76], in the hippocampus showed antidepressant-like effects [75]. Shen and colleagues found that UCMS-induced depression increased miR-221/222 expression while decreasing Cx43 expression. Genistein could decrease miR-221 and miR-222 levels in the prefrontal cortex of depressed rats while increasing Cx43 expression [77]. Chang and colleagues conducted a study examining the effect of genistein on chronic mild stress-related depression in male albino rats. Genistein administration increased sucrose preference ratio, locomotor activity, and levels of monoamines such as 5HT, norepinephrine, 5HIAA, and BDNF expression, while decreasing blood cortisol, indicating an antidepressant effect [78].

4.7. Role of GEN in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a neurodegenerative disease characterized by progressive muscle paralysis that reflects degeneration of motor neurons in the brain (primary motor cortex, corticospinal pathways, brainstem, and spinal cord). Pathologic changes in the nervous system of ALS patients involve a variety of cellular processes such as increased oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, oxidative toxicity, mitochondrial dysfunction, free radical formation, and calcium management. It occurs both sporadically and in families. Overexpression of human G93A FALS SOD-1 in transgenic mice resulted in sexual dimorphism in a mouse model of human FALS. GEN, a phytoestrogen, has neuroprotective effects in FALS mice. It should be explored as a possible preventative against pathological diseases such as ALS. Zhao et al. demonstrated that GEN exhibits neuroprotective effects in a transgenic mouse model (SOD1-G93A) of ALS, suggesting that genistein may be a promising treatment for human ALS [79]. This study shows that GEN administration downregulates the production of inflammatory mediators, improves gliosis in the spinal cord of transgenic mice, and prolongs lifespan in SOD1-G93A mice.

4.8. Role of GEN in Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)

PTSD often occurs after a traumatic experience and is one of the significant health problems associated with comorbidity, disability and increased mortality from suicidal thoughts and attempts. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disease (DSM-5) has classified PTSD as a trauma and stress-related disorder [80]. The pathophysiology of PTSD involves neurotransmitter changes, specifically a decrease in serotonin concentration in the dorsal/median raphe, likely altering the dynamics between the amygdala and hippocampus. Existing treatments for PTSD show only minimal therapeutic effect. GEN (2-8 mg/kg) modulates a variety of cellular functions, enhances serotonergic transmission, increases tryptophan hydroxylase, serotonin and phosphorylated (p)-CaMKII and

p-CREB in the amygdala. GEN treatment at doses of 2, 4, and 10 mg/kg administered intraperitoneally (i.p.) also suppressed serotonin (5-HT) levels in the brain, notably in the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus [80]. The increase in 5-HT levels due to GEN treatment could be partly associated with the 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid:5-HT ratio in the hippocampus, and it may offer a viable therapeutic approach for addressing PTSD. The impact of GEN on cognitive deficits in rats exposed to prolonged single stress (SPS) and its interaction with the serotonergic system is also examined.

5. Future directions

Further investigation is needed to fully understand the mechanisms underlying the neuroprotective effects of isoflavones, particularly genistein, in neurodegenerative diseases. *In vitro* studies have provided valuable insights into the molecular targets and pathways involved, but more preclinical and clinical research is required to validate these findings. Additionally, the optimal dosage, bioavailability, and long-term safety of genistein need to be determined for its effective translation into clinical practice. Future studies should focus on exploring the potential synergistic effects of genistein with existing pharmacological therapies or lifestyle interventions in neurodegenerative diseases. Combination therapies may offer enhanced therapeutic benefits and improve patient outcomes. Moreover, the evaluation of genistein's effects on other aspects of neurodegeneration, such as protein aggregation, synaptic dysfunction, and mitochondrial dysfunction, should be investigated. Furthermore, understanding the influence of genistein on neuroinflammation and microglial activation is crucial. In-depth investigations into the modulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, microglial activation, and neuroinflammatory pathways by genistein can provide valuable insights into its neuroprotective mechanisms and help develop targeted interventions.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, isoflavones, particularly genistein, have demonstrated potential in slowing the progression of neurodegenerative diseases. The continuously increasing prevalence of these disorders highlights the urgent need for effective therapeutic strategies. Genistein exhibits pharmacological activities relevant to neurodegenerative therapy, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and neuroprotective effects. Studies have shown that genistein can attenuate neuronal inflammation, oxidative stress, and synaptic dysfunction, while improving cognitive function and reducing neurodegeneration. It exerts its effects through modulation of various signalling pathways, including the Fas/FasL pathway, calcium signalling, and the CaM/CaMKII/CREB pathway. Despite promising findings, further research is necessary to establish the optimal utilization of genistein in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. A comprehensive understanding of its mechanisms of action, determination of appropriate dosing regimens, and evaluation of long-term safety are essential for its successful translation into clinical applications. By continuing to explore the therapeutic potential of genistein, we can advance towards the development of effective interventions to mitigate the devastating impact of neurodegenerative diseases.

References

- [1] Wu ZM, Ni GL, Shao AM, Cui R. Genistein alleviates anxiety-like behaviors in post-traumatic stress disorder model through enhancing serotonergic transmission in the amygdala. *Psychiatry Research*. 2017;255:287–91.
- [2] Lee B, Choi GM, Shim I, Lee H. Genistein prevents single prolonged stress-induced cognitive impairment in a post-traumatic stress disorder rat model via activation of the serotonergic system. *Journal of medicinal food*. 2020;23(5):476–84.
- [3] Xie J, Li X, Zhang L, Liu C, Leung JWH, Liu P, et al. Genistein-3'-sodium sulfonate ameliorates cerebral ischemia injuries by blocking neuroinflammation through the $\alpha 7$ nAChR-JAK2/STAT3 signaling pathway in rats. *Phytomedicine*. 2021;93:153745.
- [4] Williams M, McCarthy DE, Foster AC, Yednock SF, Rydel R, Messersmith E, et al. *Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry II Volume 6: Therapeutic Areas I: Central Nervous System, Pain, Metabolic Syndrome, Urology, Gastrointestinal and Cardiovascular*. Elsevier Science Limited; 2007.
- [5] Wijesekera LC, Nigel Leigh P. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*. 2009.
- [6] Terrone G, Balosso S, Pauletti A, Ravizza T, Vezzani A. Inflammation and reactive oxygen species as disease modifiers in epilepsy. *Neuropharmacology*. 2020;167:107742.
- [7] Studd J. Estrogens and depression in women. In: *Women's Health in Menopause*. Dordrecht: Springer; 1994. p. 229–31.
- [8] Singh S, Singh TG. Emerging perspectives on mitochondrial dysfunctioning and inflammation in epileptogenesis. *Inflammation Research*. 2021;70(10):1027–42.
- [9] Shen F, Huang WL, Xing BP, Fang X, Feng M, Jiang CM. Genistein improves the major depression through suppressing the expression of miR-221/222 by targeting connexin 43. *Psychiatry investigation*. 2018;15(10):919.
- [10] Qin C, Yang S, Chu YH, Zhang H, Pang XW, Chen L, et al. Signaling pathways involved in ischemic stroke: molecular mechanisms and therapeutic interventions. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*. 2022;7(1):1–29.
- [11] Mukhtar I. Inflammatory and immune mechanisms underlying epileptogenesis and epilepsy: From pathogenesis to treatment target. *Seizure*. 2020;82:65–79.
- [12] Lu LY, Liu Y, Gong YF, Zheng XY. A preliminary report: genistein attenuates cerebral ischemia injury in ovariectomized rats via regulation of the PI3K-Akt-mTOR pathway. *General physiology and biophysics*. 2019;38(5):389–97.

- [13] Lopizzo N, Zonca V, Cattane N, Pariante CM, Cattaneo A. miRNAs in depression vulnerability and resilience: novel targets for preventive strategies. *Journal of Neural Transmission*. 2019;126(9):1241–58.
- [14] Li L, Xue J, Liu R, Li X, Lai L, Xie J, et al. Neuroprotective effects of genistein-3'-sodium sulfonate on focal cerebral ischemia in rats. *Neuroscience Letters*. 2017;646:43–8.
- [15] Lee S, Jeong J, Kwak Y, Park SK. Depression research: where are we now. *Molecular brain*. 2010;3(1):1–10.
- [16] Kageyama A, Sakakibara H, Zhou W, Yoshioka M, Ohsumi M, Shimoi K, et al. Genistein regulated serotonergic activity in the hippocampus of ovariectomized rats under forced swimming stress. *Bioscience, biotechnology, and biochemistry*. 2010;74(10):2005–10.
- [17] Hu QP, Yan HX, Peng F, Feng W, Chen FF, Huang XY, et al. Genistein protects epilepsy-induced brain injury through regulating the JAK2/STAT3 and Keap1/Nrf2 signaling pathways in the developing rats. *European Journal of Pharmacology*. 2021;912:174620.
- [18] Greenberg PE, Fournier AA, Sisitsky T, Pike CT, Kessler RC. The economic burden of adults with major depressive disorder in the United States (2005 and 2010). *J Clin Psychiatry*. 2015;76:155–62.
- [19] Geronzi U, Lotti F, Grosso S. Oxidative stress in epilepsy. *Expert Review of Neurotherapeutics*. 2018;18(5):427–34.
- [20] Fazel Nabavi S, Daglia M, Tundis R, Rosa Loizzo M, Sobarzo-Sanchez E, Erdogan Orhan I, et al. Genistein: A boon for mitigating ischemic stroke. *Current topics in medicinal chemistry*. 2015;15(17):1714–21.
- [21] Dwivedi Y. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor: role in depression and suicide. *Neuropsychiatric disease and treatment*. 2009;
- [22] Chang SJ, Yu BC. Mitochondrial matters of the brain: mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative status in epilepsy. *Journal of Bioenergetics and Biomembranes*. 2010;42(6):457–459.
- [23] Chang M, Zhang L, Dai H, Sun L. Genistein acts as antidepressant agent against chronic mild stress-induced depression model of rats through augmentation of brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Brain and Behavior*. 2021;11(8):2300.
- [24] Anrather J, Iadecola C. Inflammation and stroke: an overview. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2016;13(4):661–70.
- [25] Allen CL, Bayraktutan U. Oxidative stress and its role in the pathogenesis of ischaemic stroke. *International journal of stroke*. 2009;4(6):461–70.
- [26] Ali AM, Ahmed AH, Smail L. Psychological climacteric symptoms and attitudes toward menopause among Emirati women. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2020;17(14):5028.
- [27] Akyuz E, Polat AK, Eroglu E, Kullu I, Angelopoulou E, Paudel YN. Revisiting the role of neurotransmitters in epilepsy: An updated review. *Life sciences*. 2021;265:118826.
- [28] Zesiewicz TA. Parkinson disease. *CONTINUUM: Lifelong Learning in Neurology*. 2019;25(4):896–918.
- [29] Wu HC, Hu QL, Zhang SJ, Wang YM, Jin ZK, Lv LF, et al. Neuroprotective effects of genistein on SH-SY5Y cells overexpressing A53T mutant α -synuclein. *Neural regeneration research*. 2018;13(8).
- [30] Schapira AH, Jenner P. Etiology and pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders*. 2011;26(6):1049–55.
- [31] Pierzynowska K, Gaffke L, Hać A, Mantej J, Niedzialek N, Brokowska J, et al. Correction of Huntington's disease phenotype by genistein-induced autophagy in the cellular model. *Neuromolecular medicine*. 2018;20(1):112–23.
- [32] Pierzynowska K, Gaffke L, Cyske Z, Węgrzyn G. Genistein induces degradation of mutant huntingtin in fibroblasts from Huntington's disease patients. *Metabolic brain disease*. 2019;34(3):715–20.
- [33] Morreale MK. Huntington's disease: looking beyond the movement disorder. *Adv Psychosom Med*. 2015;34:135–42.
- [34] Lu C, Wang Y, Xu T, Li Q, Wang D, Zhang L, et al. Genistein ameliorates scopolamine-induced amnesia in mice through the regulation of the cholinergic neurotransmission, antioxidant system and the ERK/CREB/BDNF signaling. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2018;9:1153.
- [35] Liu LX, Chen WF, Xie JX, Wong MS. Neuroprotective effects of genistein on dopaminergic neurons in the mice model of Parkinson's disease. *Neuroscience research*. 2008;60(2):156–61.
- [36] Lin CM, Lin RD, Chen ST, Lin YP, Chiu WT, Lin JW, et al. Neurocytoprotective effects of the bioactive constituents of *Pueraria thomsonii* in 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA)-treated nerve growth factor (NGF)-differentiated PC12 cells. *Phytochemistry*. 2010;71(17–18):2147–56.
- [37] Khan H, Singh A, Thapa K, Garg N, Grewal AK, Singh TG. Therapeutic modulation of the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinases (PI3K) pathway in cerebral ischemic injury. *Brain Research*. 2021;147399.
- [38] Jantarantotai N, Utaincharoen P, Sanvarinda P, Thampithak A, Sanvarinda Y. Phytoestrogens mediated anti-inflammatory effect through suppression of IRF-1 and pSTAT1 expressions in lipopolysaccharide-activated microglia. *International immunopharmacology*. 2013;17(2):483–8.
- [39] Gao H, Lei X, Ye S, Ye T, Hua R, Wang G, et al. Genistein attenuates memory impairment in Alzheimer's disease via ERS-mediated apoptotic pathway *in vivo* and *in vitro*. *The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*. 2022;109:109118.
- [40] Eriksen JL, Wszolek Z, Petrucelli L. Molecular pathogenesis of Parkinson disease. *Archives of neurology*. 2005;62(3):353–7.
- [41] Erekat NS. Apoptosis and its Role in Parkinson's Disease. Exon Publications; 2018. 65–82 p.
- [42] Du ZR, Gu Y, Xie XM, Zhang M, Jiang GY, Chen WF. GPER and IGF-1R mediate the anti-inflammatory effect of genistein against lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced nigrostriatal injury in rats. *The Journal of Steroid Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*. 2021;214:105989.
- [43] Cattaneo E, Rigamonti D, Goffredo D, Zuccato C, Squitieri F, Sipione S. Loss of normal huntingtin function: new developments in Huntington's disease research. *Trends in neurosciences*. 2001;24(3):182–8.
- [44] Carroll KAL, Chataway J. Understanding stroke: Pathophysiology, presentation, and investigation. *BMJ*. 2006;333(Suppl S3).

- [45] Bizzozero OA. Protein carbonylation in neurodegenerative and demyelinating CNS diseases. In: Handbook of neurochemistry and molecular neurobiology. 2009.
- [46] Bassani TB, Vital MA, Rauh LK. Neuroinflammation in the pathophysiology of Parkinson's disease and therapeutic evidence of anti-inflammatory drugs. *Arquivos de neuro-psiquiatria*. 2015;73:616–23.
- [47] Ajitkumar A, Jesus O. Huntington Disease. In: StatPearls [Internet. StatPearls Publishing; 2021.
- [48] Zheng Y, You F, Li Q, Chen J, Yang H. The effect of genistein on A β 25–35-induced PC12 cell apoptosis through the JNK-dependent Fas pathway. *Food & function*. 2016;7(11):4702–8.
- [49] Zhao Y, Zhao B. Oxidative stress and the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*. 2013;
- [50] Yu L, Rios E, Castro L, Liu J, Yan Y, Dixon D. Genistein: Dual Role in Women's Health. *Nutrients*. 2021;13(9):3048.
- [51] Wu Y, Chen M, Jiang J. Mitochondrial dysfunction in neurodegenerative diseases and drug targets via apoptotic signaling. *Mitochondrion*. 2019;49:35–45.
- [52] Wang Y, Cai B, Shao J, Wang TT, Cai RZ, Ma CJ, et al. Genistein suppresses the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway in hippocampal neurons in rats with Alzheimer's disease. *Neural regeneration research*. 2016;11(7):1153.
- [53] Uttara B, Singh AV, Zamboni P, Mahajan R. Oxidative stress and neurodegenerative diseases: a review of upstream and downstream antioxidant therapeutic options. *Current neuropharmacology*. 2009;7(1):65–74.
- [54] Tamagno E, Guglielmotto M, Aragno M. Oxidative stress activates positive feedback between the γ - and β -secretase cleavages of the β -amyloid precursor protein. *Journal of Neurochemistry*. 2008;104(3):683–95.
- [55] Spagnuolo C, Russo GL, Orhan IE, Habtemariam S, Daglia M, Sureda A, et al. Genistein and cancer: current status, challenges, and future directions. *Advances in nutrition*. 2015;6(4):408–19.
- [56] Si H, Liu D. Phytochemical genistein in the regulation of vascular function: new insights. *Current medicinal chemistry*. 2007;14(24):2581–9.
- [57] Sharifi-Rad J, Quispe C, Imran M, Rauf A, Nadeem M, Gondal TA, et al. Genistein: an integrative overview of its mode of action, pharmacological properties, and health benefits. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. 2021;
- [58] Shahmohammadi A, Rousta AM, Azadi MR, Fahanik-Babaei J, Baluchnejadmojarad T, Roghani M. Soy isoflavone genistein attenuates lipopolysaccharide-induced cognitive impairments in the rat via exerting anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory effects. *Cytokine*. 2018;104:151–9.
- [59] Riyazi SR, Nezhad YE, Fathi H, Davoudi J. Chemical properties, health benefits and threats of soy isoflavones. *Annals of Biological Research*. 2011;2(5):338–50.
- [60] Kovacs GG. Molecular pathological classification of neurodegenerative diseases: turning towards precision medicine. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2016;17(2):189.
- [61] Kim GH, Kim JE, Rhie SJ, Yoon S. The role of oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases. *Experimental neurobiology*. 2015;24(4):325.
- [62] Jung YS, Rha CS, Baik MY, Baek NI, Kim DO. A brief history and spectroscopic analysis of soy isoflavones. *Food Science and Biotechnology*. 2020;29(12):1605–17.
- [63] Hussain G, Zhang L, Rasul A, Anwar H, Sohail MU, Razzaq A, et al. Role of plant-derived flavonoids and their mechanism in attenuation of Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases: An update of recent data. *Molecules*. 2018;23(4):814.
- [64] Goh YX, Jalil J, Lam KW, Husain K, Premakumar CM. Genistein: a review on its anti-inflammatory properties. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022;13:820969.
- [65] Ganai AA, Farooqi H. Bioactivity of genistein: a review of *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy*. 2015;76:30–8.
- [66] Fujikake N, Shin M, Shimizu S. Association between autophagy and neurodegenerative diseases. *Frontiers in neuroscience*. 2018;12:255.
- [67] Dixon RA, Ferreira D. Genistein. *Phytochemistry*. 2002;60(3):205–11.
- [68] Balestrino R, Schapira AHV. Parkinson disease. *European journal of neurology*. 2020;27(1):27–42.
- [69] Wang S, Wei H, Cai M, Lu Y, Hou W, Yang Q, et al. Genistein attenuates brain damage induced by transient cerebral ischemia through up-regulation of ERK activity in ovariectomized mice. *International journal of biological sciences*. 2014;10(4):457.
- [70] Thangavel P, Puga-Olguín A, Rodríguez-Landa JF, Zepeda RC. Genistein as potential therapeutic candidate for menopausal symptoms and other related diseases. *Molecules*. 2019;24(21):3892.
- [71] Siti HN, Kamisah Y, Kamsiah JJVP. The role of oxidative stress, antioxidants, and vascular inflammation in cardiovascular disease (a review). *Vascular pharmacology*. 2015;71:40–56.
- [72] Physicians PC. Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer's Dement*. 2020;16(3):391–460.
- [73] Marini H, Minutoli L, Polito F, Bitto A, Altavilla D, Atteritano M, et al. Effects of the phytoestrogen genistein on bone metabolism in osteopenic postmenopausal women: a randomized trial. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2007;146(12):839–47.
- [74] Llibre-Guerra JJ, Prina M, Sosa AL, Acosta D, Jimenez-Velazquez IZ, Guerra M, et al. Prevalence of parkinsonism and Parkinson disease in urban and rural populations from Latin America: A community-based study. *The Lancet Regional Health-Americas*. 2022;7:100136.
- [75] Kim A, Lalonde K, Truesdell A, Gomes Welter P, Brocardo PS, Rosenstock TR, et al. New avenues for the treatment of Huntington's disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2021;22(16):8363.

- [76] Fuloria S, Yusri MAA, Sekar M, Gan SH, Rani NNIM, Lum PT, et al. Genistein: A Potential Natural Lead Molecule for New Drug Design and Development for Treating Memory Impairment. *Molecules*. 2022;27(1):265.
- [77] Chen X, Wu Y, Gu J, Liang P, Shen M, Xi J, et al. Anti-invasive effect and pharmacological mechanism of genistein against colorectal cancer. *Biofactors*. 2020;46(4):620–8.
- [78] Chávez-Fumagalli MA, Shrivastava P, Aguilar-Pineda JA, Nieto-Montesinos R, Del-Carpio. Diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease in developed and developing countries: systematic review and meta-analysis of diagnostic test accuracy. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease reports*. 2021;5(1):15–30.
- [79] Aboushanab SA, Khedr SM, Gette IF, Danilova IG, Kolberg NA, Ravishankar GA, et al. Isoflavones derived from plant raw materials: Bioavailability, anti-cancer, anti-aging potentials, and microbiome modulation. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*. 2021;1–27.
- [80] Tuli HS, Tuorkey MJ, Thakral F, Sak K, Kumar M, Sharma AK, et al. Molecular mechanisms of action of genistein in cancer: Recent advances. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2019;10:1336.

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